

PREDICTOR BIOMARKERS FOR ACUTE KIDNEY INJURY FOLLOWING EXTRACORPOREAL SHOCKWAVE LITHOTRIPSY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy (ESWL) has shown to induce acute kidney injury due to vascular and tissue damage. As real-time glomerular filtration rate is not available in developing countries, promising biomarkers are needed to prevent further tubular kidney damage. **Methods:** This systematic review design follows the PRISMA guidelines and the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions guidelines. With the keyword of acute kidney injury biomarkers following ESWL, all articles in Medline and Pubmed are analysed for inclusion in this systematic review. **Results:** There was serum creatinine (SCr), cystatin C (Cys C), kidney injury molecule-1 (KIM-1), N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG), neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL), interleukin-18 (IL-18), and homocysteine that have been studied in acute kidney injury following ESWL. Post-ESWL, SCr increased 0.26-fold ($p = 0.006$), Cys C has area under the curve (AUC) of 0.49, KIM-1 increased 3-fold ($p < 0.05$), NAG increased 4-5 fold, homocysteine increased by 4.9-fold ($P = 0.036$), NGAL increased by 0.2-fold ($p > 0.05$). Moreover, IL-18 increased post-ESWL mainly on slower shockwave. **Discussion:** It has shown that the potential acute kidney injury biomarker following ESWL including SCr, KIM-1, homocysteine, and NAG. However, as mentioned above, SCr and homocysteine have the high possibility of bias due to the presence of other diseases. KIM-1 and NAG urine could be promising biomarkers as both biomarkers increased significantly in an early stage. **Conclusion:** From many biomarkers studied following ESWL, KIM-1 and NAG were seemed to be the most potential biomarkers compared to others.

KEYWORDS biomarker, ESWL, acute kidney injury

Introduction

Extracorporeal shockwave lithotripsy (ESWL) is a minimally invasive surgical method [1] using a positive pressure of 20-110 Pa

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and negative pressure of 5-10 MPa to break small stone.[2] The resulting energy bubbles the stone and erodes it.[3] Although ESWL considered as a non-invasive, safe, and effective procedure, the energy of the pulses produced might induce tissue damage by causing inflammation on surrounding tissue.[4] Not surprisingly, as many as 3.6% of patients underwent ESWL were associated with an acute kidney injury.[5] Previous study reported that ESWL triggered acute kidney injury due to vascular damage and calcification.[6] The higher the energy, such as 200 shockwaves, the higher incidence of kidney injury post-ESWL might happen.[7] There are two mechanisms of kidney injury after ESWL including vascular injury to the kidney tissue, which causes the blood vessels to rupture therefore it would damage the kidney tubules and the release of pro-inflammatory

cytokines and harmful agents that could cause fibrosis and loss of functional tissue.[8] Moreover, the vasoconstriction of the renal vessels due to ischemic-reperfusion mechanism would induce hypoxia in some regions of the kidney tissue, which is susceptible to produce free radical during reperfusion.[9] Both of these mechanisms contribute to inflammation and destruction of renal parenchymal tissue.[10]

Post ESWL-induced acute kidney injury should be accurately measured using real-time GFR. However, this technology is unavailable throughout the region.[11] Therefore, reliable biomarkers are needed to reflect kidney tubular damage and acute kidney injury following ESWL. In a recent study, several biomarkers that seemed to have potential to predict acute kidney injury following ESWL will be discussed.

Methods

The design of this study followed the PRISMA guidelines for systematic review and meta-analysis, as mentioned in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions guidelines. A comprehensive literature search was conducted by the author to obtain relevant studies both from Medline and SCOPUS for the last ten years (January 2008 – June 2018). The author uses a search strategy with the keywords (Biomarker) AND ((Acute kidney injury) OR (Acute renal failure) OR (Kidney injury)) AND ((ESWL) OR (Extracorporeal shock wave lithotripsy) OR (Lithotripsy)).

Duplicate journals are managed using EndNote. The title and abstract of the results are reviewed, and the full texts are analysed and assessed using inclusion and exclusion criteria specified by the author. The articles are included if they contain original data from the group, clinical trials, case series of acute kidney injury biomarkers following ESWL. Only English and full-text articles are included in this study. The data is extracted from the included study using the data extraction form. Data collection including where research was conducted, methods, genetic polymorphisms studied, and outcomes. This systematic review will be presented descriptively and will discuss regarding biomarker data, general diagnostic strength as well as diagnostic strength on ESWL, and a brief description of the biomarkers.

Results

In this section, the potential biomarkers for acute kidney injury following ESWL are explained including SCr, Cys C, KIM-1, NAG, NGAL, IL-18, homocysteine as well as other potential biomarkers.

Serum creatinine (SCr)

Serum creatinine is a gold standard marker for glomerular function that increases 48-72 hours after renal injury.[11] However, SCr is found to be inaccurate in detecting acute kidney function impairment because SCr only increased significantly after the damage of nephrons for at least 50%.[12] Nonetheless, in subject with critical illness, the increased of SCr concentrations fluctuate greatly due to volume dilution, catabolic effects of critical illness, and increased tubular excretion with reduced kidney function.[13] Raikar et al. have shown in 2500 subjects underwent ESWL, showed that post-ESWL serum creatinine levels increased significantly (1.59 ± 0.44 mg/dL) compared to control (1.32 ± 0.29 mg/dL) ($p=0.006$).[14]

Cystatin C (Cys C)

Cystatin C is a 13-kDa cysteine protease inhibitor produced by all nucleated cells. Cystatin C does not bind proteins, freely filtered by the glomerulus, reabsorbed by the proximal tubule so that the normal urinary level is low.[15] The increased urinary excretion of Cys C reflects leakage from renal tubular damage. Therefore, serum Cys C has value as a urine biomarker of renal tubular injury that correlates with a decrease in GFR.[16]

In a small prospective study of 26 critically-ill patients with AKI, an increase in urinary Cys C was proven not only to predict the need for kidney transplants but also more sensitive than some other biomarkers.[17] Nejat et al. showed that the AUC for AKI was 0.84 (0.79-0.89).[18] On the other side, a meta-analysis study conducted by Yong et al. showed that the diagnostic sensitivity was 0.82 (95% CI: 0.75-0.87), specificity 0.82 (95% CI: 0.78-0.86) with AUC 0.89.[19] Cys C in serum was showed to rise slightly precede a decrease in GFR 1 to 2 days before symptoms of kidney function decline.[20] However, urine Cys C did not show significant diagnostic value in the first two days (AUC = 0.49).[21] Although promising, it should be remembered that the Cys C is partially affected by muscle mass and other demographic variables such as ethnicity.[22]

Kidney Injury Molecule-1 (KIM-1)

KIM-1 is a 38 kDa glycoprotein adhesion molecule with a cysteine domain and rich in Thr/Ser-Pro.[23] KIM-1 binds phosphatidylserine at the surface of apoptotic cells and converts tubular epithelial cells into professional phagocytes with better apoptotic cell clearance function.[24] KIM-1 is not present under normal conditions but increases in proximal tubular membrane tissue cells after an injury that serves as a compensatory mechanism.[25] Bonventre et al. indicated that the increased in KIM-1 was closely correlated with renal tubular damage.[26] Due to its predictive value as a biomarker with high sensitivity and specificity, FDA has approved the use of KIM-1 to monitor drug-induced nephropathy.[27] Meta-analysis study by Shao et al. showed the sensitivity of urinary KIM-1 content for AKI diagnosis was 74.0% (95% CI, 61.0% - 84.0%) and specificity was 86.0% (95% CI, 74.0% - 93.0%). The ROC analysis showed the area under the curve was 0.86 (0.83-0.89) for KIM-1 to predict acute kidney injury.[28] Hatipoglu et al. showed that the expression KIM-1 increased significantly two hours after ESWL compared with the control group.[29] In 40 subjects following ESWL, the KIM-1 level was found to increase slightly.[30] Fahmy et al. showed that there was a significant association between increased KIM-1 urine (6.45 SD 3.1 vs 1.96 SD 0.6) with GFR <60 mL/min/1.73m² ($p < 0.05$).[30] In ESWL subjects, regarding GFR, a significant increase of KIM-1 urine was detected, which returned to normal after two weeks after ESWL ($p < 0.01$).[31]

N-acetyl-β-D-glucosaminidase (NAG)

NAG is a tubular lysosomal based enzyme with molecular weight 130 KDa that generally cannot be filtered through the glomerulus due to its considerable molecular weight.[32] NAG will be released in the event of proximal tubular damage. NAG is considered as an outstanding epithelial predictor of necrosis tubular because of not only its level increase in tubular damage, but also it will increase shortly following injury.[33]

Han et al. showed that the diagnostic strength of NAG for the prediction of acute renal failure was 0.63.[34] In patients with a mean GFR of 78 SD $+26$ ml/min/1.73 m², it was shown that only NAG in urine was correlated significantly with an increased in

Table 1 Biomarkers for acute kidney injury after ESWL.

Biomarker	Description	Condition in human body	Normal value	Study/ies on ESWL patients	Additional information
SCr	130 kDa, produced by muscle metabolism, increase 48-72 h [11]	Increase after kidney function decline by 50% [12]	0,6-1,2 (male) 0,5-1,1 (female) [66]	Post ESWL (1.59 ± 0.44 mg/dL) vs pre ESWL (1.32 ± 0.29 mg/dL) (p=0.006).[14]	-
Cys C	13-kDa cysteine protease inhibitor, freely filtered by glomeruli [16]	Normally reabsorbed by proximal tubular cells so that it will be secreted in tubular damage[16]	Serum: 0.53-0.95 0.58–0.71[67] 0.85-0.9[68] Urine: 0.27–0.72[69] 0.61–0.83[70]	Urine Cys C did not show significant diagnostic value in the first 2 days (AUC = 0.49) post ESWL.[21]	AUC cystatin for acute kidney injury 0,84 with sensitivity of 82% and specificity of 82%.[20]
KIM-1	38 kDa glycoprotein type 1 with cysteine domain, rich of Thr/Ser-Pro	Not found under normal conditions, only in kidney tubular damage	Urine: 0.47–0.62[71] 0.64–0.91[69]	KIM-1 increase 2 hours post ESWL (p=0.01).[30] KIM-1 increase significantly (6.45 SD 3,1 vs 1.96 SD 0.6) in subjects with GFR <60 mL/min/1.73m2 (p<0.05).[31]	AUC KIM-1 for acute kidney injury 0,86.[28]
NAG	130 kDa lysosomal enzyme of kidney tubular epithelial cells [32]	Secreted in proximal tubule kidney epithelial damage[41]	Urine: 0.41–0.83[69]	NAG increase 4 times post ESWL.[37] Other study showed that NAG increase from 1.7 SD 0.68 to 1.2 SD 0.57 post ESWL and decrease 2 weeks after that.[30]	AUC NAG for acute kidney injury 0,71.[69]
NGAL	25 kDa lipocalin hydrolase protein with 8 strands binding neutrophil covalently [41]	Secreted in tubular kidney epithelial damage[41]	Serum: 0.58-0.99[73] Urine: 0.58-0.83[70]	NGAL increase un-significantly following ESWL (1,1 in first day post ESWL and 1,3 SD day 7 post ESWL).[48] Other study also showed that no significant increase of urinary NGAL in pre and post ESWL.[49]	AUC NGAL for acute kidney injury 0,71.[47]
IL-18	24-kDa IL-1 superfamily[50]	Secreted in tubular kidney epithelial inflammation[51]	Urine 0.47-0.62[72] 0.49-0.83[69]	IL-18 increase higher in those with slower shock wave.[39]	IL-18 increased significantly following acute kidney injury.[53]
Homocysteine	Amino acid with reactive sulfidril (-SH) and thiol (RSH)[54]	Secreted in tubular kidney epithelial dysfunction[55]	Urine: 0-9	Increased significantly in ESWL-induced AKI (21,01 ± 7,67 umol/L) compared those with normal kidney function (16,93 ± 7,44 umol/L) (p=0,036).[14] Other study by Demir et al. also showed homocystein increase from 9,4 ± 1,4 to 18 ± 4,8 and 11,2 ± 2,1 in 2 days and 3 months post ESWL, respectively.[56]	AUC homocysteine for acute kidney injury 0,61.[47]

GFR and ERPF, but not at KIM-1.[35] Moreover, Liangos et al. showed AUC for NAG is 0.71 (95% CI, 0.63-0.78), better than SCr (0.60, 95% CI, 0.52-0.68).[36]

Following ESWL, Danuta et al. showed a significant increase of NAG 1 day after ESWL, with a 4-fold increase (from 70.0 SD 14.7 to 285.0 SD 16.3, $p < 0.001$).[37] Rodriguez Vela et al. in 50 subjects showed that the increase in urinary NAG increased with peak 24 hours after ESWL. In addition, there was a positive relationship with the amount of shockwave, and the amount of ESWL kilo-voltage used.[38] However, Ng et al. in 206 patients with SWL 60 and 120 showed that NAG elevation was higher and was observed in the group with a slower shock wave.[39] Karslen et al. in 17 subjects after ESWL for kidney stones showed that urine levels of NAG and NGAL increased one day after ESWL and decreased after five days, but increased levels were not significant.[40] Fahmy et al. showed that there was an increase in urinary NAG after ESWL (1.7 SD 0.68 vs 1.2 SD 0.57) and decreased within two weeks after ESWL.[30]

Neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL)

NGAL is a 25-kDa lyso-chemical hydrolysate lipocaline based protein with eight strands that bind gelatinase from covalent neutrophils.[41] Under normal conditions, NGAL can be detected in small amounts with natural immune function, binding iron to decrease bacterial development.[42] In the kidney, NGAL is produced by the loop of Henle, the intercalated tubule, and the collecting duct, as well as glomerular filtration and reabsorption by the proximal tubules.[43] NGAL increases after renal injury and can be detected in serum and urine several hours before functional impairment.[44]

NGAL in urine is a promising predictor of renal failure biomarkers. NGAL is highly sensitive to renal tubular cell stress and damage as it will be activated via TLR-4 and NF-kB.[45] Regardless of it, NGAL is challenging to distinguish acute and chronic kidney injury as it is secreted in both conditions.[46] NGAL elevation will rise three hours after renal failure acute and peak about 6-12 hours after injury depending on the severity of acute renal failure.[47]

After ESWL, Zekey et al. showed that the NGAL values before ESWL were 1.1 at first day post ESWL, and 1.3 at three days post ESWL but statistically, it has no significant difference. No significant differences were identified in the NGAL and urine albumin levels of the urine from the group, even with the grouping of shock waves and the amount of shock energy on the first, second, and seventh day after SWL.[48] No significant differences were identified at the urinary NGAL level of the group before and after ESWL. In the high energy SWL group, three subjects experienced a decrease in renal function before and after ESWL.[49]

Interleukin 18 (IL-18)

Interleukin-18 is a 24-kDa cytokine belonging to the interleukin-1 superfamily. Another side, IL-18 is also produced by intercalated cells of kidney tubular epithelial cells, especially if there is any damage.[50] IL-18 is first synthesised as an inactive precursor, remained intracellular until activated by monocytes or macrophages in conditions of inflammatory tubular damage.[51] Early increase of IL-18 urine correlates with the severity of acute renal injury and mortality.[52] In a study of humans with various kidney diseases, the IL-18 urinary level was significantly higher and had a high sensitivity and specificity for the diagnosis of acute necrosis tuberculosis (ATN), compared with control.[53]

Ng et al. in 206 patients with kidney stones undergoing 60 and 120 SWL showed that IL-18 was higher in the low ESWL group.[39] However, poor IL-8 increases will be biased in the presence of diseases such as arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, psoriasis, hepatitis, and multiple sclerosis. Use of anti-IL-18 treatment may be a potential future treatment option for acute kidney injury, which can make IL-18 urine an essential additional biomarker.[51]

Homocysteine

Homocysteine is a sulfur-containing amino acid with reactive sulfhydryl (-SH) and thiol (RSH) groups and is oxidised to disulfide (RSSR) at physiological pH in the presence of oxygen.[54] Homocysteine is excreted from the body by renal and extra-renal metabolism. Renal metabolism includes urinary excretion after glomerular filtration such as creatinine. Increased levels have been associated with athero-thrombotic blood vessel disease and many other diseases including Alzheimer's disease, osteoporosis, deep vein thrombosis, and pulmonary embolism in the general population.[55]

Raikar et al. showed that in subjects patients who experienced acute kidney injury post ESWL, serum homocysteine was significantly higher in patients with acute kidney injury ($21.01 \pm 7.67 \mu\text{mol/L}$) than those who did not develop acute kidney injury ($16.93 \pm 7.44 \mu\text{mol/L}$) ($p=0.036$).¹⁴ In a study conducted by Demir et al. showed a significantly increased from 9.4 ± 1.4 to 18 ± 4.8 and 11.2 ± 2.1 in 2 days and at three months, in ESWL patients who had acute kidney injury.[56]

Other biomarkers

Other biomarkers are found to be associated with acute kidney injury, but the value of these biomarkers have not yet been studied in ESWL. L-FABP is a 14 kDa intracellular protein which expressed in the proximal renal tubules with the aim of regulating the absorption of fatty acids and intracellular transport to provide energy for the proximal tubules.[57] L-FABP is not only expressed in the liver but also in the intestines, stomach, lungs and kidney.[58] Under normal conditions, FABP can be detected at low level in the urine, but the number increases with the kidney injury. Yamamoto et al. reported that FABP in urine is a useful biomarker for predicting acute ischemic injury developing after ischemia-reperfusion injury.[59] L-FABP urine excretion thus reflects stress in proximal tubular epithelial cells, and correlation with impaired renal function has been reported with MMR after contrast nephropathy and cardiac surgery.[60] FABP was showed to have AUC 0.642 for acute renal injury.[61] Krawczeski et al. showed that L-FABP increased at 6 hours and correlated with the severity of acute kidney injury with AUC 0.77.[62] In ESWL, no studies have been conducted on this biomarker.

Gamma-glutamyl transpeptidase (GGT) and alkaline phosphatase (AP) are enzymes secreted during tubular damage and have a diagnostic strength with AUC 0.863 for acute renal failure.[63] Netrin-1 is one of the newest renal injury biomarkers, slightly expressed laminin-associated molecule in normal renal tubular epithelial cells. Netrin-1 increased 2 hours after extracorporeal circulation and peaked at 6 hours and remained elevated for up to 48 hours.[36] MCP-1 has been reported as a biomarker for the mononuclear inflammatory process that occurs after AKI-induced ischemia. In additional studies, MCP-1 has been reported as a potent chemokine produced by kidney cells and acts as a mediator of acute and toxic ischemic kid-

ney injury. In the murine model, urinary MCP-1 was found to increase significantly in intrarenal, prerenal and post-renal injury.[64] Vanin-1 is an epithelial ectoenzyme with a pantethein activity that participates in response to oxidative stress in vivo and catalyses the conversion of pantetheine to pantothenic acid and cysteamine. Vanin-1 is highly expressed in healthy human kidney and rodent tissue. The previous study found an increase in kidney-vanin-1 mRNA levels in mice with acute renal injury ischemia-reperfusion.[65]

Discussion

Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a common and potentially life-threatening condition with a definite increase in serum creatinine of ≥ 0.3 mg/dL within 48 hours or an increase of ≥ 1.5 fold or decrease in urine output to less than 0.5 mL/kg/hour in 6 hours.[74] AKI was associated with higher rates of complications, longer hospital admissions, increased mortality, and therefore more significant use of health care resources and related costs.[75] Several studies have begun to show postoperative renal function impairment urology, even on minimal operations such as ESWL.[76] ESWL was introduced in the early 1980s as a minimally invasive alternative to urinary tract surgery techniques using shock wave.[77] It was reported that ESWL could induce tissue damage by causing inflammation, haemorrhage and hemodynamic disorders that cause acute renal injury.[9,10] Acute kidney injury triggered by ESWL should be determined by using real time GFR. However, this technology is not available throughout the region.[11] This remarks the need of biomarkers that can predict acute kidney injury, especially following ESWL. These molecules can be detected in the urine or blood and indicate structural damage to the kidney.[78]

The diagnostic strength of each biomarker can be seen in table 1. SCr has an increase of 0.26 post ESWL ($p = 0.006$), Cystatin C with AUC 0.49, KIM-1 increased 3-fold ($p < 0.05$), NAG increased 4-5 fold, homocysteine increased by 4.9 ($P = 0.036$), NGAL increased by 0.2 post ESWL ($p > 0.05$), and IL-18 increased ESWL post mainly on the slower shockwave. From the results of the systematic review, it was shown that the potential acute kidney injury biomarker following ESWL was creatinine serum, KIM-1, homocysteine, and NAG. However, as mentioned above, SCr will fluctuate with other critical illnesses and only increased abruptly if the kidney function has declined under 50%.[13] Homocysteine increase can be biased by the presence of vascular, cardiovascular and Alzheimer's disease.[55] The level of KIM-1 and NAG urine can be a promising biomarker in which it is more specific. KIM-1 was found only in pathologic conditions of renal tubular damage and a significant increase in the first 2 hours.[31] On the other hand, NAG was good as a predictor of tubular epithelial necrosis because its levels only increased in tubular damage and increased in a short time.[34]

New biomarkers such as TIMP-2, IGG-7, semaphoring-3A, cysteine-rich protein-61 might be a promising biomarker for research. In this study, although the review showed potential KIM-1 and NAG urine as a biomarker, the threshold value for determining acute renal failure should be determined in future studies.[14]

Conclusion

From several ESWL-induced acute kidney injury biomarkers studied, KIM-1 and NAG were the most potential biomarkers compared to others. Future studies are urgently needed to confirm the cut-off value and the specificity of these biomarkers.

Competing Interests

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